

Orthodontic Elastics

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Abstract

Elastics have been a useful addition to any orthodontic treatment for a number of decades. Artificial Elastomers get around some of the drawbacks of natural rubber. The force extension values provided by the manufacturer for various elastic sizes are used to estimate the use of elastics in clinical practice. This review aims to assess the existing data on the various types of elastics employed in orthodontics.

Keywords: Rubber, Synthetic, Elastic Bands, Elastic Chains, Elastic Module, Elastic Separators, Force Degradation, Latex Allergy, Staining.

Introduction

Orthodontic elastics play a vital role in both intraoral and extraoral treatments. They are commonly categorized based on the direction of force they exert, such as class II or class III elastics, and can vary in length. These elastics are sourced from either natural rubber or synthetic polyurethane derived from the petrochemical industry. Both natural and synthetic rubbers share the characteristic of quickly returning to their original shape after being stretched, known as resiliency. This quality enables them to provide a continuous force for moving individual teeth or groups of teeth effectively to produce light, continuous stresses for the rotational correction, extraction space closure, diastema closure, arch consolidation, and selective midline shift.^{1,2}

History

The introduction of vulcanization by Charles Goodyear in 1839 revolutionized the utility of natural rubber, leading to a considerable expansion in its applications. Early proponents of employing natural latex rubber in orthodontics included Baker, Case, and Angle.³⁻⁶

Natural rubber In 1770, English chemist Joseph Priestley made the pivotal discovery that the substance from rubber tree known as "cahuchu", could effectively erase pencil marks, leading to its designation as "rubber". However, it was Henry A. Baker who in 1893 is credited with introducing intermaxillary elastics using rubber bands, later dubbed "Baker Anchorage." Dr. Angle

further elaborated on this technique at the New York Institute of Stomatology in 1902.

Synthetic rubber Polymers that originated from petrochemicals in the 1920s. In orthodontic applications, the majority of elastic materials currently in use are composed of polyurethane, these demonstrate resistance to heat and can endure significant stresses and pressures. In comparison to natural rubber, polyurethane rubbers boast excellent strength and resistance to abrasion.

Classification

Elastics can be classified in many ways. According to their availability, the material, there uses, force.⁷⁻¹¹

According to the Materials

1. Latex elastics
2. Synthetic elastics

According to the Availability Elastic Bands

1. According to lumen size
 - $2/16'' = 1/8'' = 3.18\text{mm}$
 - $3/16'' = 3/16'' = 4.76\text{mm}$
 - $4/16'' = 1/4'' = 6.35\text{mm}$
 - $5/16'' = 5/16'' = 7.94\text{mm}$
 - $6/16 = 3/8'' = 9.5\text{mm}$
 - $8/16'' = 1/2'' = 12.7\text{mm}$
 - $10/16'' = 5/8'' = 15.8\text{mm}$
 - $12/16'' = 3/4'' = 19.1\text{mm}$
2. According to the Force
 - High pull: It gives 71 gm force (2½ oz)

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- Medium pull: It gives 128 gm or 4½ oz force
- Heavy pull: It gives 184 gm or 6½ oz force.
- 3. According to colour- Manufacturer based.
- 4. According to use-
- Intraoral Elastics : Intramaxillary Elastics- Class I elastics , also known as horizontal elastics, are positioned in the same side of the arch anteroposterior.
Intermaxillary Elastics- Intraoral elastics placed in both arches, classified into Class II, III, Crossbite and Openbite elastics and others like Midline (Alexander) elastics.
- Extraoral Elastics

Elastics Chains

Also called power chains. These filaments come in three different configurations based on the length of the filament: closed, short, and long.

Elastic Ligatures

Also known as modules/ 'O' rings. Modules are small ring elastics used to secure the arch wires to the orthodontic bracket.

Elastic Thread and Elastic Sleeves

Round thread composed of silk or nylon with a non-porous, smooth surface is available. It uses a gentle, constant, persistent, and predictable force.

Similar to thread, elastic tubing has a hollow core, used to cover arch wires in areas where teeth are absent or unerupted thus preventing irritation to soft tissues.

Elastic Separators

These are ring-shaped elastics that are placed in between two teeth, no more than two weeks, in order to create space between the teeth for the placement of molar bands.

Force Degradation

Following a thorough analysis of the elastomeric chain literature, it can be concluded that the majority of commercially available elastomeric chains typically lose between 50% and 70% of their initial force on the first day of load application. After three weeks, only 30-40% of original force was retained. In an in-vivo study, fifty percent of force degradation occurred in the first 4 to 5 hours of latex elastics, followed by continuous and gradual force degradation for the remaining time intervals.¹²⁻¹⁷

Disadvantages of Elastics

- Absorbs water from saliva.
- Cytotoxicity.
- Discoloration and staining.
- Latex allergy.^{18,19}

Conclusion

Elastics rank among the most adaptable materials at an orthodontist's disposal, serving as an invaluable tool in their arsenal. Failing to fully utilize these materials means not fulfilling the patient's needs adequately. In fact, it's difficult to envision practicing this branch of dentistry effectively without incorporating this essential material.

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